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Environmental lifecycle impact assessment for CULTURAL-E climate and cultural based solution sets

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Abstract. The situation reported from the Global Status Report 2021 and the now war-related risks urge the application of measures for decreasing emissions and energy consumption, aiming carbon neutrality by 2050. Smart solutions for decreasing energy consumption are researched and implemented in the context of energy efficient buildings and Plus Energy Houses (PEHs). As PEHs gained an increasing consideration for the challenge of energy consumption reduction, their design produced a multitude of solutions. In such a multitude, an optimum is defined by accounting and comparing the performance offered by provided technologies and the actual technical requirements. The latter can be affected by the geographical/climate context as well as the user behaviour and socio-cultural aspects. This objective has been addressed in the CULTURAL-E research framework. Furthermore, in compliance with the current climate targets, this framework attributes a central role to the environmental performance of systems designed for PEHs. In this work, environmental impacts' investigations of solution sets for PEHs are provided according to the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology. The developed bottom-up approach provides lifecycle information hierarchically on three levels (component, solution sets and PEH), while information of operation energy is derived through building energy simulations and average user-related energy usage. The selected 8 case studies are drawn from the CULTURAL-E research and include solution sets tailored for climate and socio-cultural clusters. Innovative technological components as well as conventional technologies are included. Based on such analyses, an environmental (CO₂) payback periods have been estimated, i.e., the time required to recoup the total expended embodied CO₂ through building operation carbon positivity. Results identified potentials for climate mitigation and different performance levels of the implemented technologies and photovoltaics systems, especially for countries in which a faster shift to renewable energy sources is needed for meeting the 2050's environmental targets.

Keywords: Plus Energy Houses; Life Cycle Assessment; LCA.

1. Introduction

Despite the efforts and the record levels of renewable energy sources in the European contexts, the construction industry still presents a slower shift away from the direct use of coal, oil and traditional biomass towards renewable sources. According to the 2021 Global Status Report for Building and Construction, the pandemic-induced changes [1] and now war-related risks, which had consequences also on the energy demand during the building operation and related CO₂ emissions. This change reflects a shift from the commercial and retail sectors to the residential sector. For these reasons some

initiative have been already undertaken (REPowerEU plan [2]) and the next five years are critical and require a wide adoption of transformational approaches and a full stakeholders' engagement to create a zero-carbon built environment.

In this context, energy efficient buildings (passive, zero energy) offer new perspectives for a concrete reduction of energy consumption and consequent emissions during building operation. Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs) has received increasing attention in recent years. Their potential has been discussed in studies, while not yet demonstrated [3–5]. Furthermore, due to novelty of such building systems, their environmental relevance of this concept has been often questioned [6]. In fact, PEBs may present higher amount of materials and installation components, such as storage elements and photovoltaic systems, which in a lifecycle perspective must be accounted in order to evaluate the environmental potential of the whole building [6]. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) analyses provide adequate tools for the quantification of environmental impacts over the building lifecycle, i.e., by taking into account fabrication of components, construction, operation, maintenance, dismantling and waste [7, 8].

For this reason, LCA analyses have been included and claimed relevant in the CULTURAL-E framework. CULTURAL-E aims to present modular and replicable solutions for residential buildings, i.e., Plus Energy Houses (PEHs). The presented solutions match selection and interaction of technologies to cultural and climate aspects, by fostering energy savings. The latter is allowed with the application of renewable energy sources (RES), photovoltaic panels - and thermal solar collectors to be coupled with storage systems. Among all results, CULTURAL-E aims to reduce not only energy consumption during the building operation, but also the life cycle impacts over the building lifecycle while improving indoor environment quality. One of the objectives of the work is to develop technologies and climate-cultural tailored solution sets for PEHs. Lastly, as a further step, LCA in CULTURAL-E provides the analysis on the whole building level and, more specifically, on cultural-climate designed demo cases. This allows the identification of hotspots for the environmental assessment and the derivation of benchmarks for PEHs to be used by stakeholders as reference values[4].

In this work, outcomes from LCA of cultural-climate tailored solution sets are presented. Results should be considered as preliminary for the following Building LCA. With respect to this, environmental information on installation components has been collected. When necessary, the lifecycle modelling was carried out on the basis of data provided by technologies producers. Afterwards a technologies set has been allocated in 2 exemplary buildings and 4 different climate-cultural contexts. Energy simulations have been carried out and average cultural-related energy consumption has been also considered through occupancy behavior model [9]. Totally, 8 case studies have been considered, which serve for understanding advantages of solution sets in different contexts. Results showed that a specific solution set can provide a different performance level in each context and energy positivity is not always achieved. Where a positive energy balance is derived, the building system allows a payback of initial environmental investment. However, reasonable payback periods are not necessarily achieved. In such an eventuality, different design strategies need to be considered by producers as well as designers.

2. Lifecycle Assessment of PEHs in CULTURAL-E

Through LCA (ISO 14040 – 14044) it is possible to evaluate potential environmental impacts associated with identified inputs and releases over all the stages of a product's life[7, 8]. The basic idea of LCA is to solve problems that have already arisen or are arising and not to "shift" them from one life cycle phase to the next ("shift of burdens" concept).

In the field of construction, supplementary standards for Building LCA have been established. In EN 15804 [10], core rules for the product category and Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) are presented, while EN 15978 presents the calculation method [11]. For building LCA, most applications consider 3 levels of assessments, which are:

- **Product level:** the single product
- **Functional system level:** consists of different components/products of a building, which together can perform a specific function.

- **Building level:** collects all important building constructions and systems and information on building operation

Within CULTURAL-E, a more suitable framework for LCA has been established, which complies also with the overall work structure. Firstly, the three abovementioned levels are translated as here following:

- **Technology component:** the single developed technology.
- **Solution set:** the set, which envisages heating/cooling/ventilation systems.
- **(Plus Energy) Building:** PEB system, provided with the technologies and a solution set.

• **Figure 1.** Overview of LCA analysis and assessment levels in CULTURAL-E.

The LCA analysis follows a bottom-up approach (Figure 1), starting from the modelling of a technology. Once provided, all environmental information of needed products, functional systems and solution sets can be modelled with products and components belonging to them. Finally, the sum of the information regarding functional systems and building operation will provide the LCA analysis on the building level. Furthermore, LCA analyses for CULTURAL-E technologies are decontextualized from the building or a specific user or use destination. This implies that their climate and cultural contexts are in a first instance not considered. On the contrary, for higher solution sets and building levels, analyses are carried out by considering a specific social and climate context. To this purpose, energy simulations in several climate areas are carried out. Finally, information on cultural-related energy usage is also required.

3. Case study and results

3.1. Goal and scope of the analysis

For the analysis, an exemplary solution set (SS) has been conceived and located in a low rise (LR) and high rise (HR) building and 4 climate contexts. Totally, 8 cases have been considered and are here presented. The solution set entails the following building installations components together with abbreviations here consistently used (see also Table 1):

- Power Generator for domestic hot water (DHW), space heating (SH) and cooling (SC) - PWG
- Thermal energy storage - TES
- SH/SC Distribution - DISTR
- Ventilation system – VEN
- Pipework, Valves, Circ. Pumps, Heat Exchanger - PIP
- Photovoltaics system - PV

Table 1. Solution set description and specification for low-rise (LR) and high rise (HR) buildings.

Component type	Specifications	LR	HR
PWG	Air-Water heat pump - heating, cooling, DHW by fresh water stations	50 kW	150 kW
TES	Water Storage+ Heating/Cooling buffer in stainless steel units – XPS insulation	1000 l + 500 l Buffer	3000 l + 1500 l Buffer
DISTR	Low temperature fan coil, free cooling	950 W	950 W
VEN	Ventilation and air treatment		
PIP	Copper pipes with XPS insulation. Stainless steel elements (Valves, Circulation pumps and Heat exchanger)	ø52cm x 3m ø38mm x 10m ø38mm x 10m	ø52cm x 3m ø38mm x 22m ø38mm x 22m
PV	Average technology with battery, sized to provide a positive balance	240 m ² (estimated)	528 m ² (estimated)

The selected 4 reference - climate contexts are *Mediterranean* (Italy – IT), *Continental* (Germany – DE), *Oceanic* (France– FR) and *Subarctic* (Norway– NO).

Low rise example is a 663 m² 3-floors' building, provided with 7 dwellings, each between 80-110 m² net surface. High rise example is a 2912 m² 7-floors' building, with 40 dwellings, each one between 55-80 m² net surface.

For the considered systems, the LCA has been specified according to [7, 8]. The chosen functional unit is m²*year. This in order to understand the share of the provided installation over the whole building system. The analysed impact category is Global Warming Potential (GWP) 100 years (IPCC GWP100a) - kg CO₂ eq. [10]), while other environmental indicators will be provided in other extensive works. The considered lifespan duration is limited to 30 years, which can cover the average service life for building installations. Here in Table 2, LCA specifications are summarized.

Table 2. LCA specification for the CULTURAL-E solution sets.

LCA specifications (based on ISO 14044[7, 8])	
Object	Functional system: solution sets aimed for PEHs
FU (functional unit)	1 m ² *y
Lifespan duration	30 years
System boundary	- product stage (modules A1-A3), - Energy operation (module B6) - EoL stage (modules C3-C4) and benefits (module D)[11]
Impact categories	Global Warming Potential 100 years (IPCC GWP100a) [kg. CO ₂ eq.][10]
Environmental database	Ökobau.dat[12] , Environmental Product Declaration (EPDs)

The modelling has been carried out through the GENERIS® tool of Fraunhofer Institute for Building Physics (IBP) [13], by using generic environmental databases for construction sector [12] as well as product-specific datasets. For the assessment of the building operation, information on national electricity mix and CO₂ conversion factors have been collected from the European Energy Agency (EEA) [14].

3.2. Lifecycle inventory (LCI)

According to designers' specifications, for each building type the following total components were collected (Table 3). This information serves as basis for the calculation of the embodied impacts (lifecycle modules: raw material extraction and production A1-A3; waste C3-C4; credits due to recycling D according to [11]).

Table 3. Lifecycle inventory of solution sets for low rise (LR) and high rise (HR) buildings.

Component	LR	HR
	Total	Total
PWG [unit]	1	1
TES [unit]	1	1
VEN [unit]	3 units* apartment	3 units* apartment
DISTR [items]	38 IT, 39 DE, 36 FR, 44 NO	121 IT, 115 DE, 137 FR, 103 NO
PIP	1300 kg copper 0,2 m ³ XPS	3000 kg copper 0,5 m ³ XPS
PV [m ²]	240	528

Operational energy (B6 module [11]) is derived through building energy simulations on the 4 climate contexts. The total energy demand considered DHW, SH and SC. Results are summarized in Table 4 for LR and Table 5 for HR building.

Table 4. Energy simulation results for LR buildings.

LOW RISE	Mediterranean (IT)	Continental (DE)	Oceanic (FR)	Subarctic (NO)
Qth_user	36.9	33.3	35.3	85.5
Qel_HP	14.1	14.4	13.3	17.7
Qth_HP	47.8	41.1	46.3	48.1
Qel_APL	29.7	31.3	39.6	34.8
Qel_LGT	0.9	0.7	1.2	1.1
Qel_VEN	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.7
Qel_CF	1.1	0.7	1.3	0.8
Qel_aux	0.4	0.5	0.4	1.1
Qel_FNC	2	2.2	2.3	3.3
Total energy demand	+52	+53.6	+61.8	+62.5
PV surface (m ²)	172.5	177.6	204.9	207.0
PV credits	-72.35	-72.42	-72.38	-72.45
Energy balance	-20.4	-18.8	-10.6	-10.0

Table 5. Energy simulation results for HR buildings.

HIGH RISE	Mediterranean (IT)	Continental (DE)	Oceanic (FR)	Subarctic (NO)
Qth_user	28.9	27.1	34.4	31.9
Qel_HP	9.8	10.3	10.3	12.8
Qth_HP	36.2	31.7	44.1	37.3
Qel_APL	23.6	26.9	35.6	30.6
Qel_LGT	1.1	0.8	1.9	1.4
Qel_VEN	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.4
Qel_CF	1.6	1.1	1.7	1
Qel_aux	2.4	1.8	8.3	3
Qel_FNC	1.4	1.3	2.5	2
Total energy demand	+42.2	+44.6	+62.7	+53.1
PV surface (m ²)	614.14	649.43	913.48	772.84
PV credits	-36.28	-36.26	-36.24	-36.28
Energy balance	+5.9	+8.3	+26.5	+16.8

Accordingly, the useful thermal energy provided to the whole building - end users (DHW + SH + SC) has been calculated (Qth_user), by considering all thermal losses. Qth_HP is the thermal energy

generated by the heat pump (DHW + SH + SC). Furthermore, energy usage consumption (Q_{el}) of the single component has been derived. This includes appliances (APL), lighting (LGT), ventilation (VEN), ceiling fans (CF), auxiliary energy (aux) and fan coils (FNC). The user behaviour has been implemented in the different profiles for occupancy, plug loads and lightning usage. The climatic context has been while considered by using different climatic data, and different building envelopes. The derivation of the total energy demand allowed a first preliminary sizing of PV modules in terms of power (kWp) and surface (m²). With respect to this, 1000 kWh/year for 1 kWp installed (0.2 kWp/m²) were considered as a conservative assumption.

When the calculated total energy balance is negative, as for LR buildings, the functional system produces more energy than its own demand and is aimed therefore for PEHs.

The energy production occurs through PV modules installed exclusively on the roof. When the energy balance is positive, as for HR buildings, there is criticality due a limited roof surface for PV modules. Not surprisingly, the climate area dictates the annual solar yield and the consequently reached PV credits. Another interesting outcome is related to the installations' usage, which seems to be higher in Subarctic example. This cultural aspect might be further investigated and proven with up-to-date data.

3.3. Lifecycle impact assessment (LCIA)

Here in Table 6, results of the lifecycle impact assessment (LCIA) are shown. Impacts are specified for each installation component and determined for each building type.

Table 6. LCIA: Solution sets embodied impacts (A1-A3; C;D modules [11]) in LR and HR buildings.

Component	LR	HR
	GWP [kg CO ₂ eq.]	GWP [kg CO ₂ eq.]
VEN	970.0	3233
PWG	1417.3	3543
TES	282.2	546.8
PV	54528	163584
Tot. embodied [impact/m²]	111.8	57.36
Tot. embodied [impact/m²*y]	3.762	1.948

Table 7. LCIA: Operational impacts of LR and HR buildings in the different cultural-climate context.

National Electricity mix [kg CO ₂ eq./kWh]	Mediterranean (IT)		Continental (DE)		Oceanic (FR)		Subarctic (NO)	
	LR	HR	LR	HR	LR	HR	LR	HR
	0.285		0.337		0.057		0.027	
Tot. B6 [kg CO₂ eq./m²*y]	-5.80	1.69	-6.34	2.81	-0.60	1.51	-0.31	0.52

Lastly, Table 7 shows operational impacts for each building type and climate context, by taking into the account national electricity mixes and their respective impacts [14].

3.4. Results evaluation and discussion

As shown in the LCIA results, constructive aspects and therefore embodied impacts can significantly influence the overall lifecycle impact, and photovoltaic modules are main contributor. By accounting embodied impacts only, HR buildings perform a better environmental profile. This is due to an optimized installation of components and larger net floor area for a given building footprint.

Operational impacts related to energy demand only are higher in continental/subarctic climate areas and low-rise buildings. High rise buildings present in this respect also an optimized thermal energy and electricity consumption. However, due to a higher number of potential users and a more limited roof surface, they should use other surfaces, aiming at a positive energy balance.

In one hand, PV modules contribute mostly to the total assessed embodied impact. Their environmental performance can be therefore questionable. On the other hand, they are source of renewable energy during the whole functional system lifespan. In terms of environmental impacts and GHG emissions, they allow credits by avoiding emissions related to energy consumption coming from non-renewable sources. Applying an economic analogy, PV systems can help to “pay-back” an initial environmental climate “investment”. Based on the derived results, environmental payback periods (PB) are here provided for each of the considered 8 case studies. This quantity allows also to highlight the advantages of solution sets for PEH and serves as a further indicator for decision-makers.

Figure 2. Environmental payback periods of solution sets in LR buildings.

energy mix in Continental area may lead while to similar outcomes. In conclusion, PB periods are primarily affected by the national carbon intensities of electricity generation.

4. Conclusion

This work presented outcomes from LCA analyses carried out on cultural and climate tailored solution sets drawn from the project CULTURAL-E. This study highlighted differences in terms of performance level of the designed installations and solution sets. It identified effects related to 1) technologies and design choices, 2) cultural-climate context and 3) national energy generation.

In the first instance, the LCIA results proved that photovoltaics systems and their technology level are relevant for the achievement of the system’s carbon neutrality. PV modules have in fact the highest share of embodied emissions on the solution set level. Moreover, design choices, and more specifically, the designed building type may dictate also the operational energy: within high rise buildings, other surfaces besides roofs need to be spotted aiming at a positive energy balance.

A further barrier for positive operational energy balances is represented by the climate-cultural area. Due to their temperatures and lower annual solar yields, Continental and Subarctic area can reach, in fact, less energy credits. In comparison with, e.g., Mediterranean area, Subarctic area recorded also higher installations’ usage. This cultural aspect deserves however further and in-depth investigations.

Lastly, national energy generation influence primarily the estimated payback periods. In particular, national carbon intensity of electricity production can determine the effectiveness of PEHs, as valuable solutions to accelerate the shift to renewable energy sources. In this study, a higher effectiveness of the investigated solution sets is found in the Italian and German contexts. For these contexts and such, the implementation of PEHs should be especially encouraged in a very short term and the energy mix can be improved after adding local PV to make each building rewarding by itself. Where, on the contrary, the national energy grid presents a low carbon intensity, strategies aimed to decrease rather the initial

climate investment should be detected. This may reduce the environmental payback period, by allowing the exploitation of the carbon positivity and increasing also stakeholders' willingness to PEHs. In the overall, such analyses need to be addressed also on the whole building level and need to be enhanced also with inclusions of other aspects (e.g. cost). The derivation of environmental and economic values on exemplary climate and cultural-based PEHs will provide feedbacks to designers' choices and, lastly, make available enhanced benchmarks on PEHs.

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